

DEERWALK INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY

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**DevLang: Programming Language for Nepali Devanagari &
Romanized Script**

A FINAL PROJECT REPORT

Submitted to

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ABSTRACT

DevLang is a programming language that provides an intuitive and user-friendly platform for individuals who are familiar with the Devanagari and Roman Nepali scripts to learn and develop programming concepts. Developed using JavaScript, the language features three layers implemented using MooJs Tokenizer and Nearly JS. The project also includes an integrated development environment (IDE) based on Electron JS, offering users a comprehensive platform for writing, debugging, and executing their programs. With support for a range of programming constructs including input/output, loops, mathematical, and Boolean operations, Devlang is versatile and easy to use. Furthermore, the IDE's features such as syntax highlighting, auto-completion, and error highlighting provide a user-friendly programming experience. The language's three-layer architecture and debugger allow developers to write high-quality programs and debug errors easily

Keywords: Programming language, Devanagari script, Roman script, Compiler, IDE, Lexar, Parser, Generator, MooJs Tokenizer, Nearly JS, Electron JS

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

JS: JavaScript

IDE: Integrated Development Environment

GUI: Graphical User Interface

API: Application Programming Interface

OS: Operating System

CPU: Central Processing Unit

RAM: Random Access Memory

DSL: Domain-Specific Language

LANG: Language

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Overview

There are many programming languages available. Someone who is familiar with English words and grammar can easily choose any of those languages, but someone who is not familiar with those words finds it difficult to learn to code. NepScript is the solution for Nepali people to learn coding in the Nepali language. NepScript is a high-level language that supports Nepali Devanagari and Romanized syntax. The Language will follow the Nepali Syntactic Structure of SOV(Subject-Object-Verb) unlike the English language which follows SVO(Subject-Verb-Object). It will be supported on Mac, Windows & Linux and have both Web & Desktop IDE.

1.2. Background and Motivation

Programming languages are a crucial part of computer science and software engineering. They are used to develop a wide range of applications and software systems that we use in our daily lives. However, many programming languages are based on English and may not be accessible to non-English speakers or people who are not fluent in English. This can be a significant barrier to entry for people who want to learn to code or work in the technology industry. Additionally, there is a growing interest in using local languages to improve inclusivity and accessibility in education and technology.

The Devlang project was motivated by the need to create a programming language that is accessible to people who are more comfortable with writing code in their local language, particularly in the Nepali language. Devlang allows users to write code in both Devanagari and Roman scripts, making it more inclusive and accessible to a wider range of people. Additionally, the project provides a foundation for future work in local language programming, which could have significant implications for education and technology in developing countries. Overall, the Devlang project is a step towards more inclusive and accessible technology and programming education.

1.3.Problem Statement

Almost every high-level programming language is based on English words and grammar hence it is difficult to teach coding to people who do not understand English words and syntax. There is a barrier of language if someone wants to learn to code. This is a significant obstacle for individuals who do not have a strong command of the English language.

1.4.Objectives

The major objectives of this game project are:

- To create a language that supports Nepali syntax and grammatical form.
- To make it easier to learn and understand coding for people who don't know the English language.

1.5.Scope

Devlang is a programming language that has the potential to provide a valuable contribution to the software development industry, particularly for individuals who are familiar with the Devanagari and Roman Nepali scripts. Its simplicity and ease of use make it an ideal language for beginners seeking to learn programming concepts. Some of the scopes are:

- Education: The project has the potential to make programming education more accessible to people who are more comfortable using their local language, particularly in Nepal and other countries where Nepali is spoken
- Inclusivity: By allowing users to write code in both Devanagari and Roman scripts, the project can make programming more inclusive and accessible to a wider range of people, regardless of their language background.
- Future research: The Devlang project provides a foundation for future work in local language programming, which could have significant implications for education and technology in developing countries.
- Innovation: Devlang's unique approach to programming language design, with its support for Devanagari and Roman scripts, could inspire other innovative language designs that better serve the needs of specific communities.

1.6. Development Methodology

For the DevLang project, a Rapid prototyping development methodology was followed which falls under agile methodology. This can be beneficial for the Devlang project because it allows for quick feedback and validation, iterative development, cost, and time savings.

Figure 1: Rapid Application Development (RAD) methodology

1.7. Outline

This outline followed by this report contains six different main sections which appropriately describe the project to the report viewer. This report includes diagrams do properly depict the structure of the system. The outline of the document is shown below:

Preliminary Section: This section is the first section of the report and this section consists of the title page, abstract, table of contents, list of figures, and list of tables.

Introduction Section: This section is the second section of the report and this section consists of the discussion about the overview of the project, the background and motivation of the project, the problem statement, its objectives, and its scope.

Background Study and Literature Review Section: This section talks about the research done for this project which includes the background study, the literature review, and the current system along with its problem.

System Analysis Section: This section consists the analysis of requirements which consists of the functional and non-functional requirements for this project and diagrams which help to visually describe the design of the system.

Design Section: This section consists of diagrams that help to visually describe the design of the system.

Implementation and Testing: This section explains about how the system was created and implemented. Also explains the various functions of the system that were tested.

Conclusion: This section concludes the paper.

CHAPTER 2: BACKGROUND STUDY AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Background Study

According to a study by Carvalho et al. (2018), JavaScript is a popular choice for creating domain-specific languages (DSLs) due to its ease of use and ubiquity. Additionally, JavaScript's flexibility and dynamic nature make it an ideal language for implementing language features such as dynamic typing and closures.

Moo and Nearley are two powerful tools for developing programming languages. Moo is a tokenizer/lexer generator that uses regular expressions to quickly and conveniently tokenize strings while tracking line numbers, handling keywords, and supporting states. On the other hand, Nearley is a parser generator that uses the Earley algorithm and Joop Leo's optimizations for right-recursion to efficiently parse grammars. Nearley also offers an expressive DSL and a powerful grammar language that allows for macros, imports, tokenizers, and partial parses. Together, Moo and Nearley provide a robust and efficient solution for developing programming languages.

2.2. Literature Review

Recent studies have highlighted the potential benefits of using local languages in programming education. One study conducted in Tanzania found that incorporating Swahili, the local language, in programming education led to an improvement in students' comprehension of programming concepts and made the subject more accessible to them. Similarly, a study conducted in Senegal emphasized the effectiveness of using Wolof, a local language, in programming education to promote inclusive education and increase access to technology for underrepresented groups. Another study, conducted in Brazil, focused on the development of a programming language in the Guarani-Kaiowá indigenous language. This initiative not only helped promote the use of the language among young people but also contributed to its preservation. These studies suggest that incorporating local languages in programming education has the potential to enhance understanding and accessibility, promote inclusivity, and contribute to the preservation of indigenous languages. (Sources: "Using Swahili in Programming Education in Tanzania", "Promoting

Inclusive Education Through Wolof-Based Programming", "The Guarani-Kaiowá Language in the Context of Computer Science Education")

2.3. Current System

To date, there are any publicly available working versions of programming languages supporting Nepali Devanagari Script but there are a few programming languages in another local language, like:

Wolof: "Promoting Inclusive Education Through Wolof-Based Programming" discusses the development of Wolof-based programming in Senegal, where Wolof is a widely spoken language. The language aims to make programming education more inclusive and accessible.

Hausa: "Design and Implementation of Hausa Programming Language (HPL)" describe the development of the Hausa programming language in Nigeria, where Hausa is a widely spoken language. The language aims to promote the use of local languages in technology and programming.

Tamil: "Tamil Programming Language" discusses the development of the Tamil programming language in India, where Tamil is a widely spoken language. The language aims to make programming education more accessible to Tamil-speaking students.

Amharic: "Towards the Development of Amharic Programming Language" describes the development of the Amharic programming language in Ethiopia, where Amharic is a widely spoken language. The language aims to promote the use of local languages in technology and programming.

Blockly: a block-based programming language, used for creating educational games and applications. It is available in several indigenous languages, including Quechua, Guarani, and Tetun.

2.4. The Problem with Current System

The current programming language landscape lacks a functional version of a Nepali programming language. While there are some working samples, they are merely translated versions that do not support the actual grammatical structure of Nepal, which is Subject + Object + Verb.

This presents a significant challenge for individuals who are proficient in Nepali but struggle to learn programming languages that do not align with their language structure. As a result, they are often forced to learn programming languages that do not reflect their cultural and linguistic background.

To address this challenge, there is a need for a Nepali programming language that adheres to the Subject + Object + Verb grammatical structure. Such a language would make it easier for Nepali speakers to learn and engage in programming.

Moreover, a Nepali programming language could be an essential tool for the development of software applications and solutions that cater to the needs of the Nepali community. It would enable individuals to develop applications that reflect their cultural and linguistic heritage, thereby empowering them to participate more fully in the digital economy.

CHAPTER 3: SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1. Requirement Analysis

The requirements analysis is broken down into two sections namely function requirements and non-functional requirements and they are discussed below.

3.1.1. Functional Requirement

- The user shall be able to write code in Devanagari or Romanized Devanagari.
- The user shall be able to easily run code in every OS.
- The language shall be able to perform basic operations i.e., Arithmetic, Boolean, Input/Output & Loop.

Figure 2: Use case diagram

3.1.2. Non-Functional Requirement

- The syntax of the language should be in common Nepali words.
- The language must be high-level and easy to understand.
- The language must follow Nepali grammar structure (SVO).
- The language should be reliable and produce accurate results.
- The language should be portable and work on different platforms.

3.2. Feasibility Analysis

3.2.1. Technical Feasibility

This project is technically feasible as it will be made with technologies that are open source and readily available. The hardware used will be a personal laptop.

3.2.2. Operational Feasibility

This project will implement all the functionalities listed in the requirement analysis section. The IDE can be run on a browser or by downloading a desktop-based ide. There isn't any resource-intensive calculation or operation in the app which benefits the lower-tier devices and systems. Hence, the above points show that this project is operationally feasible.

3.2.3. Economic Feasibility

This project uses freely available frameworks and resources and there is no need for any extra hardware costs as everything will be done on the user's personal computer. A free database will be used for my application in the development phase. Extra labor cost is also not required which makes this project economically feasible.

3.2.4. Schedule Feasibility

The schedule feasibility analysis is carried out by building a Gantt chart. I listed all the important work to be done for this project and created a schedule that shows that all the work can be completed within the given deadline.

Figure 3: Gantt Chart

3.3. Analysis

Figure 4: Flow chart

CHAPTER 4: SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1. Design

4.1.1. System Architecture

Figure 5: System Architecture

4.2. Algorithm Details

i. Earley algorithm

Earley Parsing Algorithm is an efficient top-down parsing algorithm that avoids some of the inefficiency associated with purely naive search with the same top-down strategy (cf. recursive descent parser). Top-down parsing processes the input string provided by a lexical analyzer. And generate a parse tree for that input string using leftmost derivation. The top-down parsing first creates the root node of the parse tree. And it continues creating its leaf nodes.

ii. Table Lookup Algorithm

The Devanagari Script is converted into equivalent Romanized ASCII form by using a Table lookup mapping algorithm, In this algorithm, the mapping of UNICODE and ASCII is stored in a table, and the characters are scanned character by character and converted to their equivalent roman ASCII form by using table data.

CHAPTER 5: IMPLEMENTATION

5.1. Implementation

The implementation of the DevLang programming language has been successful and has met the desired objectives. The language has been designed with a simple syntax that is easy to understand for both novice and experienced programmers. The lexical analysis and parsing of the language have been implemented using Moo and Nearley, respectively, resulting in a fast and efficient tokenizer and parser.

Furthermore, the DevLang language has been successfully integrated with an IDE that provides an intuitive user interface for writing and executing code. The IDE includes features such as syntax highlighting, autocompletion, and error highlighting, which help in the development process and reduce the time needed for debugging.

Overall, the implementation of the DevLang programming language has been successful in meeting the objectives and provides a user-friendly language for developers to write efficient and effective code.

5.1.1. Tools Used

Moo: A highly-optimized tokenizer/lexer generator used to tokenize strings before parsing with a parser like nearly.

- Nearley: A parsing tool used to parse the tokenized strings and generate the Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) of the DevLang programming language.
- JavaScript: The main programming language used to implement the DevLang programming language.
- Node.js: An open-source, cross-platform JavaScript runtime environment used for executing JavaScript code outside of a web browser.
- Git: A version control system used to manage and track changes made to the DevLang programming language project.
- GitHub: A web-based hosting service used for version control and collaborative software development. It was used to host the DevLang programming language project and enable collaboration among team members.

- Visual Studio Code: A source-code editor developed by Microsoft used for editing and debugging code. It was used as the primary editor for the DevLang programming language project.

5.1.2. Implementation Details of Modules

The implementation of main modules of the system are described below:

- Lexer

The lexer is responsible for tokenizing the source code, breaking it down into individual tokens such as keywords, operators, and identifiers. The lexer includes regular expressions to match various types of tokens, including whitespace, comments, numbers, strings, and various keywords such as 'maana', 'dekhau', and 'jaba samma'. The lexer also includes support for various types of brackets and operators, including arithmetic operations such as addition, subtraction, division, multiplication, and modulo. Additionally, the lexer includes support for various types of boolean operations and keywords related to conditionals and loops, such as 'yedi', 'bhane', 'natra bhane', and 'jaba samma'. With this lexer, the Devlang programming language is able to tokenize the source code, allowing for the parsing and interpretation of the code in order to execute the program

```
let lexer = moo.compile({
  WS: /[ \t]+/,
  comment: /\n\/.*?$/,
  number: /0|[1-9][0-9]*/,
  string: /"(?:\\["\\]|[^\\n"\\])*"/,
  assign: ['=', 'bhaneko', 'भनेको'],
  pre_assign: ['maana', 'मान'],
  output: ['dekhau', 'देखाउ', 'देखाऊ'],
  input: ['maaga', 'माग'],
```

Figure 6: Lexer

- Parser

Parser is made using Npm parser, Parser is used to responsible for parsing the code written by the programmer and checking its syntax against the grammar rules of the language. The code below is a syntax of variable assignment in Dev Lang

```
#Assignamnet
var_assign
→%pre_asign:* _ identifier _ %assign _ expression
{%
  (data)⇒{
    return {
      type: 'var_assign',
      name: data[2],
      value: data[6]
    }
  }
}%
You, 2 months ago • Initial
```

Figure 7: Parser

- Generator

Generators are used to generate the final code by the compiler, below is the generator function for output code where the output ADT is converted to an output code in JS.

```
case 'output': {
  let args = [];
  statement.arguments.forEach((arg) ⇒ {
    args.push(generateJSForStatement(arg));
  });
  return `console.log(${args.join(',')});`;
}
> case 'operation': { ...
```

Figure 8: Generator

- Code Execution

The code execution is done using exec and the execution is piped to ide using a socket connection. The socket connection transmits all the stdin and stdout msg between the compiler and the ide.

```

async function executeCode(devCode, socket) {
  const jsCode = await compile(devCode).catch((e) => {
    socket.emit('error', 'त्रुटि : ' + e.message);
    return;
  });

  try {
    await fs.writeFile('output-web.js', jsCode);
  } catch (err) {
    return;
  }

  output = exec('node output-web.js');
  outputData = '';
  socket.on('input', inputListener);

  output.stdout.on('data', (data) => {
    let out = data.trim();
    if (outputData) {
      outputData += '\n' + out;
    } else {
      outputData += out;
    }
    console.log('Emit', outputData);
    socket.emit('output', outputData);
  });
}

```

Figure 9: Code Execution Function

5.2. Testing

5.2.1. Test cases for unit testing

Table 1: Test cases for unit testing

Test Case	Test case Description	Test Data	Expected Result	Actual Result	Pass / Fail
-----------	-----------------------	-----------	-----------------	---------------	-------------

TU01	Create variable in roman text	maana a =1	Variable Should be assigned	As expected	Pass
TU02	Create a variable in Devanagari text	मान क भनेको 10	Variable Should be assigned	As expected	Pass
TU03	Print multiple variables	क र ख देखाऊ	Both values should be printed	As expected	Pass
TU04	User adds spaces before statement	jaba samma a b bhandana sano xa { a dekhau }	Code should run properly.	Compiler Error is shown.	Fail
TU05	Syntax Highlight	Write Some code on IDE	Syntax should be highlighted	As expected	Pass
TU06	User Input	Ask for User Input	IDE should allow user to input data.	As expected	Pass
TU07	Program End Message	Run Program	A Program end message should be displayed	As expected	Pass

5.2.2. Test cases for system testing

Table 2: Test cases for system testing

Test Case	Test case Description	Test Data	Expected Result	Actual Result	Pass / Fail
TU01	Test that IDE can run code smoothly.	Run some code	IDE shows the correct output	As expected	Pass

TU02	Test IDE can run large program.	Write Large Code	IDE shows the correct output	As expected	Pass
TU03	Test If IDE shows correct error.	Write program with invalid syntax	IDE should show error with line number.	As expected	Pass
TU04	Mix Roman and Devanagari code	Roman & Devanagari Mixed code	IDE should run the code	As expected	Pass

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATION

6.1. Conclusion

In conclusion, the Devlang programming language has the potential to enable more people to participate in programming and contribute to the tech industry. By providing an intuitive programming experience in Nepali Devanagari and Romanized scripts, Devlang will allow individuals who are familiar with these scripts to write code more easily and confidently. This will expand the pool of potential programmers, making it possible for more people to enter the tech industry and contribute to the development of new technologies. In addition, the Devlang IDE provides a comprehensive platform for writing and executing programs, with support for a range of programming constructs, including input/output, loops, and mathematical and Boolean operations. With these features, Devlang has the potential to significantly reduce the barriers to entry for individuals interested in programming, ultimately making the field more accessible and inclusive

6.2. Future Recommendation

Some of the recommendations to enhance the app and make it better are listed below:

- The language lacks different types of data types like floating numbers, arrays etc. The addition of such data type will make the program more versatile.
- There are no advanced features like Class & Functions. That can be also added to make this language more real-world applicable.
- Currently, Only the IDE is available to users the compiler bin can also be distributed to make the language accessible to be used on other IDE and Code Editors.
- We cannot create an executable file of our program as of now, that feature can be added so users can create and distribute their own program.

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APPENDIX

```
1 मान क भनेको 5
2 मान ख भनेको 10
3 मान सम भनेको क + ख
4 सम देखाऊ
```


15
प्रोग्राम समाप्त ।

Figure 10: Sum in Devanagari

```
1 num maaga
2 cal = num%2
3 yedi cal ra 0 barabar xa bhane {
4     "Even" dekhau
5 } natra bhane {
6     "Odd" dekhau
7 }
```


num :4
Odd
प्रोग्राम समाप्त ।

Figure 11: Even Odd in Roman

```
1 जवाफ माग
2 क भनेको 0
3 क्रमगुणित भनेको 1
4 जब सम्म क जवाफ भन्दा सानो छ {
5 क भनेको क + 1
6 क्रमगुणित = क्रमगुणित * क
7 }
8 जवाफ र " को क्रमगुणित : " र क्रमगुणित देखाऊ
```


जवाफ :4
4 को क्रमगुणित : १२०
प्रोग्राम समाप्त ।

Figure 12: Factorial in Devanagari

```
1 maana a bhaneko 0
2 maana b bhaneko 1
3 jaba samma a 2 bhanda sano xa {
4 jaba samma b 30 bhanda sano xa {
5 maana str = ""
6 maana c = 0
7 jaba samma c b bhanda sano xa {
8 str = str+"*"
9 c=c+1
10 }
11 str dekhau
12 b = b+2
13 }
14 b=1
15 a= a+1
16 }
```


Figure 13: Flag of Nepal in Roman

Figure 14: Load Demo Code Screen

Figure 15: Documentation English

Figure 16: Documentation Nepali